

Hot spots near the Flecher and Venezia applicators investigated with an alternative method

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Abstract

An alternative method is presented to investigate the dose field near the CTV_HR. The results were compared to the quantities used in CT-based brachytherapy.

Introduction

The CT-MR image-based HDR gynecological brachytherapy dosimetry protocols are based on the use of the quantities: the dose values of 2ccm volumes in the Bladder, Rectum, and Sigmoid. This study aimed to examine the dose field in the OARs near the Flecher and Venezia applicators with our presented method.

Material and Methods

We generated 10 cervix treatment plans with the Oncentra Brachy ver.4.5.4 (Elekta b.v.) brachytherapy planning system using manual graphical optimization. The objectives were: to achieve lower dose values to the 2ccm OAR volumes, than the prescription dose (5Gy). To investigate the dose fields near the CTV_HR, in addition to the contours Bladder, Rectum, and Sigmoid, we generated the following structures: the extension of the CTV_HR by 5 mm in every direction (ctv05), the intersections of the structure ctv05 with the Bladder, Rectum, and Sigmoid, referred to as *ib*, *ir*, and *is* respectively. These structures represent the volumes of the OARs' sections being near the CTV_HR, as illustrated in Fig.1. We obtained the recently accepted quantities from the DVH diagrams: the dose values to the 2ccm volumes in OARs, as well as, the dose values of the 10% and 90% volumes in the structures *ib*, *ir*, and *is*, summarized in Table 1. The DVH diagram of the brachytherapy plan #8 is illustrated in Fig.2.

Fig.1. The intersection structures *are* (upper), *ib* (middle), and *ir* (lower image).

Results

Fig.2. DVH diagram of the brachytherapy plan #8.

Patient #	Bladder d2ccm Gy	Rectum d2ccm Gy	Sigmoid d2ccm Gy	ib10 D V10% Gy	ib90 D V90% Gy	ir10 D V10% Gy	ir90 D V90% Gy	is10 D V10% Gy	is90 D V90% Gy	CTV_HR V 5Gy %
1	3,3	4,84	4,4	4,2	3,2	6	3,6	4,88	3,05	88,8
2	4,78	3,17	3,57	6,1	4,18	5,2	3,9	4,75	3,3	88,1
3	4,34	4,8	4,25	4,7	2,16	6,2	4,3	5,1	2,5	86
4	4,8	3,7	4,31	6,1	4,2	5,5	4,3	6,3	3,6	92
5	5,2	4,3	3,5	6,4	4,3	5,5	4	4,8	2,1	81
6	3,9	1,6	3,5	5,4	4,2	5,5	4	5,3	4,8	89
7	4,7	4,2	3,6	6	4,7	5,5	5	4,3	2,9	83
8	5	4,8	2,3	7,4	3,7	5,7	3,6	3,6	1,6	70
9	1,6	5,2	4,8	5,2	3,2	6,2	4,6	6,3	3,8	97
10	4	4	3,4	5,2	3,2	6,2	3,9	4,9	3,4	87

Table 1. The 2ccm volume dose values in the OARs, and the dose values of 10% and 90% volumes of the intersection structures.

Fig.3. The 2ccm volume dose values in the OARs (blue), and the dose values of 10% (brown) and 90% (yellow) volumes of the intersection structures listed in Table 1.

The brachytherapy plans fulfilled the objectives: the dose values to 2ccm volumes in the Bladder, Rectum, and Sigmoid were below 5.2 Gy. The dose level in 90 % of the volumes of the intersection structures was typically 4Gy, while 10% of the *ib*, *ir*, and *is* volumes received typically 6Gy, range [5,5-7,4 Gy].

Conclusion

In about 50% of the BT plans, the dose values in hot spots in the intersection structures *ib* and *ir* were 120% higher than the prescription dose.

The introduced intersection structures could be a useful tool to estimate the dose values in the Bladder, Rectum, and Sigmoid wall being near the CTV_HR.

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